

Monte Carlo Estimation of the Linear-Discontinuous Finite-Element Flux in Tetrahedral Meshes Using Collision-Based Functional Expansion Tallies

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a theoretical framework for estimating the 3D linear-discontinuous finite-element flux and corresponding statistical uncertainties for tetrahedral-mesh Monte Carlo particle-transport simulations. The method leverages tetrahedral meshes for accurately modeling complex geometries and uses particle collision locations within tetrahedral elements to compute spatial moments. After the simulation, these spatial moments are used to construct the linear-discontinuous finite-element flux. Unlike conventional element-averaged tallies, this approach provides sub-element spatial resolution and significantly reduces flux errors. The framework is verified using two cube-geometry test cases, demonstrating that collision-based LDFE flux reconstruction can reduce pointwise flux errors by up to an order of magnitude.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, tetrahedral, mesh, finite element, functional expansion

1. INTRODUCTION

The Monte Carlo N-Particle (MCNP[®]) transport code supports the use of tetrahedral meshes to model complex geometries and simulate radiation transport [1]. Currently, the scalar flux in tetrahedral-mesh MCNP simulations is estimated using elemental “edits”, which are element-averaged tallies that provide a single average value for the scalar flux for each tetrahedral element. These “edits” offer limited spatial resolution and can lead to significant pointwise errors in regions with strong flux gradients, such as near material boundaries.

Recently, it has been shown that functional expansion tallies can be used to approximate the linear-discontinuous finite-element (LDFE) flux, which estimates the flux at an even finer resolution than the spatial resolution of the mesh, and is capable of reducing the pointwise flux error by an order of magnitude [2].

Unlike [2], this study uses collision-based functional expansion tallies [3] to compute spatial moments of the scalar flux. These moments are then used to construct the collision-based estimate of the LDFE flux. Also, unlike [2], this method was implemented and tested by running tetrahedral-mesh MCNP simulations and post-processing the collision events (recorded in PTRAC files) [1]. Together, the MCNP software and the post-processing tool provide the ability to model radiation transport at high resolution in space, angle, energy, and time, by combining the ability to:

- model complex geometries using unstructured meshes,
- sample from continuous distributions in energy, angle, and time,
- provide a finite-element estimate of the scalar flux.

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2. THEORY

2.1. Spatial Flux Moments in a Tetrahedron

As defined in [2], the spatial flux moments for a tetrahedral element are

$$m_i = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \phi(\vec{r}) b_i(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}, \quad (1)$$

where

V is the volume of the tetrahedral element,

\vec{r} is position,

$\phi(\vec{r})$ is the scalar flux as function of position \vec{r} ,

$b_i(\vec{r})$ is the i^{th} barycentric coordinate as function of position \vec{r} ,

m_i is the spatial moment of the scalar flux corresponding to the i^{th} barycentric coordinate.

It is worth noting that for linear tetrahedral elements the barycentric coordinates are mathematically equivalent to isoparametric coordinates.

2.2. Collision Estimator for the Spatial Flux Moments

In a Monte Carlo particle transport code, the spatial flux moments can be statistically estimated via

$$m_i \approx \frac{1}{VW} \sum_c \frac{w_c b_i(\vec{r}_c)}{\Sigma_t(\vec{r}_c)} \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}, \quad (2)$$

where

m_i is the spatial moment of the scalar flux corresponding to the i^{th} barycentric coordinate,

V is the volume of the tetrahedral element,

W is the total starting weight of all particles,

c is any collision that occurs within the tetrahedral element,

w_c is the weight of the particle that caused collision c ,

\vec{r}_c is the location of collision c ,

$b_i(\vec{r}_c)$ is the i^{th} barycentric coordinate of the collision location \vec{r}_c ,

$\Sigma_t(\vec{r}_c)$ is the total macroscopic cross section at the collision location \vec{r}_c .

This approach is particularly convenient for post-processing MCNP PTRAC files to directly convert discrete collision events into flux estimates.

2.3. Linear-Discontinuous Finite-Element Flux in a Tetrahedron

For tetrahedral nodal LDFE, the spatial basis functions are simply the barycentric coordinates. Thus, the LDFE flux is simply a linear interpolation of the nodal flux values,

$$\phi(\vec{r}) \approx \phi_1 b_1(\vec{r}) + \phi_2 b_2(\vec{r}) + \phi_3 b_3(\vec{r}) + \phi_4 b_4(\vec{r}), \quad (3)$$

where

ϕ_i is the nodal flux (evaluated at the i^{th} vertex),

$b_i(\vec{r})$ is the barycentric coordinate corresponding to the i^{th} vertex evaluated at position \vec{r} .

Because the flux is allowed to be discontinuous, the nodal fluxes ($\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3, \phi_4$) are local and do not need to match adjacent tetrahedral elements. However, in theory, for smooth solutions and sufficiently large number of particle histories, the nodal flux discrepancies between adjacent elements should be small. Conversely, for strong nonlinear gradients, noticeable discontinuities are expected and are not necessarily a deficiency of the method. This locality of LDFE simplifies computation and makes the method well-suited for unstructured tetrahedral meshes. The tetrahedral barycentric coordinates (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) are also local, and specify the location of a point within a single tetrahedron. If a point \vec{r} is located on the i^{th} vertex, then the i^{th} barycentric coordinate is equal to one and all other barycentric coordinates are zero. If all barycentric coordinates have a positive value less than one, then the point is located within the tetrahedral element, and if any barycentric coordinate is negative, then the point is outside of the tetrahedral element. The conversion from Cartesian coordinates to tetrahedral barycentric coordinates is described in detail in [4].

Note that for the global LDFE solution, the value of the flux at a vertex is not uniquely defined if multiple tetrahedral elements share that vertex; this avoids enforcing artificial continuity constraints across element boundaries for the global solution.

2.4. Constructing the Linear-Discontinuous Finite-Element Flux

After running a Monte Carlo simulation in which the geometry is modeled using a tetrahedral mesh, the spatial flux moments can be used to determine the scalar flux at the nodes (vertices) of each tetrahedral element. For the LDFE formulation, these moments only contribute to the local element's nodal fluxes, eliminating coupling between adjacent elements and simplifying the algebraic system.

This derivation starts by substituting the LDFE approximation for the scalar flux, Eq. 3, into the spatial-moment equation, Eq. 1,

$$m_i = \frac{1}{V} \int_V [\phi_1 b_1(\vec{r}) + \phi_2 b_2(\vec{r}) + \phi_3 b_3(\vec{r}) + \phi_4 b_4(\vec{r})] b_i(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}, \quad (4)$$

which can be expanded further to get equations for the four spatial moments,

$$\begin{cases} m_1 = \frac{\phi_1}{V} \int_V b_1(\vec{r}) b_1(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_2}{V} \int_V b_2(\vec{r}) b_1(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_3}{V} \int_V b_3(\vec{r}) b_1(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_4}{V} \int_V b_4(\vec{r}) b_1(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \\ m_2 = \frac{\phi_1}{V} \int_V b_1(\vec{r}) b_2(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_2}{V} \int_V b_2(\vec{r}) b_2(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_3}{V} \int_V b_3(\vec{r}) b_2(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_4}{V} \int_V b_4(\vec{r}) b_2(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \\ m_3 = \frac{\phi_1}{V} \int_V b_1(\vec{r}) b_3(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_2}{V} \int_V b_2(\vec{r}) b_3(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_3}{V} \int_V b_3(\vec{r}) b_3(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_4}{V} \int_V b_4(\vec{r}) b_3(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \\ m_4 = \frac{\phi_1}{V} \int_V b_1(\vec{r}) b_4(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_2}{V} \int_V b_2(\vec{r}) b_4(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_3}{V} \int_V b_3(\vec{r}) b_4(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{\phi_4}{V} \int_V b_4(\vec{r}) b_4(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Next, one can use the property for tetrahedral barycentric coordinates,

$$\frac{1}{V} \int_V b_i(\vec{r}) b_j(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} = \begin{cases} 1/10 & \text{for } i = j \\ 1/20 & \text{for } i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

to finish deriving the system of equations for the nodal fluxes

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1/10 & 1/20 & 1/20 & 1/20 \\ 1/20 & 1/10 & 1/20 & 1/20 \\ 1/20 & 1/20 & 1/10 & 1/20 \\ 1/20 & 1/20 & 1/20 & 1/10 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \\ \phi_3 \\ \phi_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} m_1 \\ m_2 \\ m_3 \\ m_4 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

Next, Eq. 7 can be solved by inverting the matrix on the left side of the equation,

$$\begin{pmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \\ \phi_3 \\ \phi_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 16 & -4 & -4 & -4 \\ -4 & 16 & -4 & -4 \\ -4 & -4 & 16 & -4 \\ -4 & -4 & -4 & 16 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} m_1 \\ m_2 \\ m_3 \\ m_4 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

2.5. Computing the nodal flux variances analytically

The nodal flux variances are computed from the variances and covariances of the spatial moments,

$$\mathbf{V}_\phi = \text{diag}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{C}_m\mathbf{A}^\top). \quad (9)$$

where

$$\mathbf{V}_\phi = \begin{pmatrix} \text{Var}(\phi_1) \\ \text{Var}(\phi_2) \\ \text{Var}(\phi_3) \\ \text{Var}(\phi_4) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}^\top = \begin{pmatrix} 16 & -4 & -4 & -4 \\ -4 & 16 & -4 & -4 \\ -4 & -4 & 16 & -4 \\ -4 & -4 & -4 & 16 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_m = \begin{pmatrix} \text{Var}(m_1) & \text{Cov}(m_1, m_2) & \text{Cov}(m_1, m_3) & \text{Cov}(m_1, m_4) \\ \text{Cov}(m_2, m_1) & \text{Var}(m_2) & \text{Cov}(m_2, m_3) & \text{Cov}(m_2, m_4) \\ \text{Cov}(m_3, m_1) & \text{Cov}(m_3, m_2) & \text{Var}(m_3) & \text{Cov}(m_3, m_4) \\ \text{Cov}(m_4, m_1) & \text{Cov}(m_4, m_2) & \text{Cov}(m_4, m_3) & \text{Var}(m_4) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

Note that this uncertainty propagation formulation neglects correlations between different collisions occurring within the same particle history.

The variance of the LDFE flux at an arbitrary point within a tetrahedral element can be obtained through barycentric-coordinate-based interpolation of the nodal flux variances. Furthermore, the standard deviation of the LDFE flux can then be determined by taking the square root of the variance.

2.6. Estimating the nodal flux variances using batch statistics

The nodal flux variances can also be estimated using batch statistics. In this approach, the simulation is divided into N statistically independent batches, each containing an equal number of particle histories. The nodal fluxes are computed for each batch, and the ensemble of batch results is then used to estimate the sample mean and variance of each nodal flux.

3. RESULTS

This paper includes two test cases. Both cases model particle transport in a unit cube ($0 \leq x, y, z \leq 1$) filled with a purely absorbing medium ($\Sigma_t = \Sigma_a = 1$), and have analytical solutions. Because a cube can be exactly partitioned into tetrahedra, any discrepancies between the mesh-based Monte Carlo simulations and the analytical reference solutions can be attributed solely to statistical noise and the limitations of the flux reconstruction method rather than geometric error.

The Cubit[®] software [5] is used to generate a mesh composed of 12 tetrahedral elements, shown in Fig. 1. This mesh is used for both test cases, and is generated using the following Cubit commands:

```
brick x 1 y 1 z 1  
volume 1 scheme tetmesh  
volume 1 size 1  
mesh volume 1
```


Figure 1. Cubit-generated mesh used for both test cases, consisting of 12 tetrahedral elements. The black lines represent anterior tetrahedral-element edges. The gray lines represent interior and posterior tetrahedral-element edges.

The MCNP software is used to simulate 10^8 particle histories for both test cases [1]. The collision events are recorded in a PTRAC HDF5 file by including the following PTRAC card in the MCNP input file:

```
ptrac file=hdf5 flushnps=1e6 event=col
```

A Python script post processes the PTRAC HDF5 file to load the (x, y, z) coordinates of collision events and their corresponding weights, w . The script also reads the mesh data from the XDMF file. The script then iterates over each collision coordinate and determines the element index that contains the collision coordinate. For each element, the script computes the barycentric coordinates (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) of the collision point with respect to the element's vertices. The contribution to the spatial moments (m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4) are then computed using Eq. 2. Next, the script computes the nodal fluxes $(\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3, \phi_4)$ for each element using Eq. 8. Lastly, the script plots a 2D slice of the 3D LDFE solution.

3.1. Test Case 1: Normally Incident Beam

The first test case includes a normally incident particle beam uniformly distributed on the bottom face of the cube with a flux of $1 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The analytical reference solution in the purely absorbing medium ($\Sigma_t = \Sigma_a = 1$) is

$$\phi(z) = \exp(-z). \quad (13)$$

Figure 2. Plots of the 2D scalar flux at $y = 0.25$ based on element-averaged tallies (left), LDFE reconstruction (middle), and the analytical reference (right) for test case 1.

The MCNP simulation for the first test case generated a PTRAC HDF5 file with 6.32×10^7 collision events and a file size of 7.78 GB. Figure 2 compares the element-averaged flux, the collision-based LDFE reconstruction, and the analytical reference for a 2D slice through the plane $y = 0.25$ for test case 1. Relative L2 error norms are computed for both the element-averaged flux and LDFE flux values on a $100 \times 100 \times 100$ array of points uniformly spaced in the unit cube. The relative L2 error norm for the element-averaged flux is 0.1558, and the relative L2 error norm for the LDFE flux is 0.0153. Also, the maximum relative error for the element-averaged flux is 0.8811, and the maximum relative error for the LDFE flux is 0.2066. Both of these error metrics demonstrate that the LDFE reconstruction leads to significant error reduction compared to element-averaged fluxes.

Using Eq. 9, the average relative standard deviation for the nodal fluxes is estimated to be 0.0017, whereas, using batch statistics, as described in Section 2.6, the average relative standard deviation is estimated to be 0.0020. The close agreement between analytical and batch-derived standard deviations confirms that the uncertainty propagation method accurately reflects the true Monte Carlo noise. Furthermore, because the standard deviation is small, the pointwise error in the LDFE reconstruction is predominantly deterministic.

3.2. Test Case 2: Uniform Isotropic Source

The second test case includes a uniformly distributed isotropic extraneous source, with a source strength of $1 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and has reflective boundaries on all faces except for the top face of the cube. This cube with reflective boundaries is mathematically equivalent to a slab that is infinite in the x and y dimensions and spans -1 to 1 in the z dimension. The analytical reference solution can be derived from citation [6] for the purely absorbing medium ($\Sigma_t = \Sigma_a = 1$),

$$\phi(z) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 E_1(|z - z'|) dz', \quad (14)$$

which further simplifies to

$$\phi(z) = 1 - \frac{1}{2} E_2(z + 1) - \frac{1}{2} E_2(1 - z), \quad (15)$$

where E_n is the exponential integral defined as

$$E_n(u) = \int_1^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-ut)}{t^n} dt. \quad (16)$$

Figure 3. Plots of the 2D scalar flux at $y = 0.25$ based on element-averaged tallies (left), LDFE reconstruction (middle), and the analytical reference (right) for test case 2.

The MCNP simulation for the second test case generated a PTRAC HDF5 file with 7.65×10^7 collision events and a file size of 9.41 GB. Figure 3 compares the element-averaged flux, the collision-based LDFE reconstruction, and the analytical reference for a 2D slice through the plane $y = 0.25$ for test case 2. Relative L2 error norms are computed for both the element-averaged flux and LDFE flux values on a $100 \times 100 \times 100$ array of points uniformly spaced in the unit cube. The relative L2 error norm for the element-averaged flux is 0.0721, and the relative L2 error norm for the LDFE flux is 0.0214. Also, the maximum relative error for the element-averaged flux is 0.6081, and the maximum relative error for the LDFE flux is 0.3536. Once again, these error metrics demonstrate that the LDFE reconstruction leads to significant error reduction compared to element-averaged fluxes.

Using Eq. 9, the average relative standard deviation for the nodal fluxes is estimated to be 0.0016, whereas, using batch statistics, as described in Section 2.6, the average relative standard deviation is estimated to be 0.0016. Similar to test case 1, the agreement between analytical and batch-derived standard deviations for test case 2 confirms that the uncertainty propagation method accurately reflects the true Monte Carlo noise. Furthermore, because the standard deviation is small, the pointwise error in the LDFE reconstruction is predominantly deterministic.

4. CONCLUSION

This study helps bridge the gap between discrete Monte Carlo tallies and continuous finite-element representations by deriving a theoretical framework for computing LDFE fluxes from collision events in Monte Carlo simulations. The approach is implemented in a Python-based post-processing tool that reconstructs the LDFE flux directly from MCNP-generated PTRAC files.

The framework is verified using two cube-geometry test problems, which demonstrate that the collision-based LDFE reconstruction substantially improves spatial accuracy relative to element-averaged flux

tallies. In particular, the relative L2 error norms are reduced by approximately one order of magnitude for the first test problem and by a factor of 3.4 for the second test problem.

Beyond these verification studies, the proposed framework offers a promising path toward more accurate radiation transport simulations in complex geometries, particularly for resolving strong spatial gradients at sub-element scales. However, the current formulation is limited to linear finite elements on tetrahedral meshes, since it relies on barycentric coordinates. Extending the method to other element types, such as pentahedral or hexahedral meshes, would require reformulating the spatial basis functions as well as the LDFE reconstruction procedure using other coordinate systems.

Future work will focus on applying the framework to more complex geometries, assessing figure-of-merit performance, integrating the method directly into the MCNP source code, and generalizing the approach to higher-order finite elements.

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